

LEGISLATIVE AUTONOMY AND GOOD GOVERNANCE OUTCOMES IN NIGERIAN STATES: A STRUCTURAL FUNCTIONALISM ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Legislative autonomy remains a crucial component of democratic consolidation and good governance in federal systems. In Nigeria, the quest for functional State Houses of Assembly has intensified due to increasing and excessive dominance of the executive, weak legislative capacity and the inability of the state legislatures to effectively perform their constitutionally assigned duties. This paper examines the nexus between legislative autonomy and good governance outcomes in Nigerian States through the theoretical lens of Structural Functionalism. The paper analyses how the functional capacity of state legislatures in Nigeria's Fourth Republic has been compromised by limited autonomy, thereby affecting their capacity to perform essential functions for maintaining democratic stability and development. Drawing on documentary analysis of constitutional provisions, judicial rulings, reform efforts such as Executive Order 10 and existing scholarship, the paper reveals that inadequate financial and administrative independence of State Houses of Assembly undermines legislative oversight, transparency, accountability and service delivery of the state level. The findings also indicate that political interference has really inhibited the independence and effectiveness of state legislature. The paper concludes that full legislative autonomy is indispensable for strengthening democratic governance, enhancing fiscal responsibility, promoting rule of law and delivering public sector reforms. Recommendations include constitutional enforcement mechanisms, strengthening internal legislative bureaucracy, fiscal discipline frameworks and robust civic engagement.

INTRODUCTION

The democratic governance landscape in Nigeria's fourth Republic, which began in 1999, presents a unique paradox of sustained civilian rule alongside persistent governance challenges. Despite being the longest democratic period in the country's history since independence, the quality of governance at the states level remains unsatisfactory, characterized by limited accountability, inadequate public service delivery and pervasive corruption (Olaogun, Iwuoha Umoren, Idoko & Chiazor;2025). Within this context, the role of state legislatures as critical institutions for promoting good governance has attracted scholarly attention, particularly regarding how their operational autonomy influences governance outcomes. This article argues that the constrained autonomy of state legislatures in Nigeria significantly impedes their functional capacity, thereby adversely affecting governance outcomes.

The concept of legislative autonomy encompasses financial independence, operational self determination and institutional capacity to perform constitutional responsibilities without undue interference from the executive branch. In Nigeria's federal structure, state legislatures are constitutional mandated to perform core functions including lawmaking, representation and oversight of the executive. However, evidence suggests that many state legislatures operate under significant constraints that limit their effectiveness in fulfilling these roles (Abifarin & Atidoga, 2006). The persisted dominance of state governors over legislative processes, often facilitated by constitutional ambiguities and political practices has raised fundamental questions, about the functionality of Nigeria's democratic separation of powers.

This paper adopts structural functionalism as its theoretical framework to analyse how legislative institutions contribute to maintaining Nigeria's democratic system. Structural functionalism views society as a complex system whose parts work in harmony to promote stability and solidarity (Barnard, 2000). From this perspective, legislatures perform specific functions essential for maintaining social equilibrium, including interest aggregation, conflict resolution and system maintenance. When these institutions cannot perform their functions adequately due to structural limitations, the entire system experiences dysfunction, manifesting as governance deficits (Gomez – Diago, 2019).

Recent developments in Nigeria's political landscape including the Supreme Court ruling on Local Government Autonomy and ongoing constitutional review efforts, highlight the timely relevance of examining legislative autonomy (Yakubu, 2025; Asiegbu, 2025). While much attention has focused on local government autonomy, less scholarly work has systematically analysed state legislative autonomy using a robust theoretical framework. This paper addresses this gap by examining how structural functionalism can illuminate the governance relationship between legislative autonomy and governance outcomes in Nigerian states. It conceptualizes the state legislative system as an indispensable organ within the governance organism. When its autonomy is compromised, the overall system becomes dysfunctional, leading to poor governance outcomes such as ineffective oversight, corruption, weak rule of law and limited service delivery.

The paper answers the following questions:

- i. What is the current state of legislative autonomy of Houses of Assembly in Nigeria.
- ii. How does legislative autonomy enhance good governance in Nigeria states?
- iii. What functional roles do state, houses of Assembly play in the governance system?
- iv. How does structural functionalism explain the consequences of limited autonomy?
- v. What structural reforms are necessary to ensure effective legislative functioning?

The paper argues that legislative autonomy is not merely a constitutional aspiration but a structural necessity for democratic governance.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Legislative Autonomy

Ameh (2020) describes legislative autonomy as the extent to which legislatures operate independently – financially, administratively and institutionally – without undue executive interference. It is the right of a legislature to self – govern, which means it can operate independently from other branches of government, particularly the executive, without external interference (PLAC,2023). Legislative autonomy includes:

- **Financial autonomy:** control over budget preparation, disbursement and expenditure
- **Administrative autonomy:** Power to recruit and manage legislative staff
- **Operational autonomy:** Freedom to determine legislative agenda and internal proceedings.

Legislative autonomy strengthens the separation of powers by ensuring that the legislature can act as a true check on the executive branch. With the necessary resources and authority, a legislature is better equipped to make quality laws and conduct meaningful oversight. It allows the legislature to better represent the will of the people, as it is not limited by external pressure or influence.

Despite constitutional provisions and efforts to enact it, full financial and administrative autonomy for state legislatures remains a challenge in the country, with executive dominance and financial dependence being persistent issues (Akewushola, 2024).

Good Governance

Good governance is the process by which public institutions conduct public affairs, manage public resources, and ensure human rights are realized effectively, transparently and without corruption. It is a system of values, policies and institutions that allows a society to manage its affairs in a responsive, inclusive and transparent way (UNDP, 2021). The World Bank defines it as the manner in which power is exercised in the management of a country's economic and social resources for development, encompassing public sector management, accountability, transparency and the rule of law (World Bank, 1992). It involves the processes by which governments are selected and replaced the capacity of the government to effectively implement sound policies, and the respect for institutions that govern social and economic interactions (Kaufman & Kray, 2002).

Good governance has eight(8) major characteristics. It is participatory, consensus oriented, accountable, transparent, responsive effective and efficient, equitable and inclusive and follows the rule of law. It assures that corruption is minimized, the views of minorities are taken into account and that the voices of the most vulnerable in society are heard in decision making. It is also responsive to the present and future needs of society (UN-ESCAP, 2017). The purpose of good governance is to strengthen public institutions to be capable, responsive, inclusive and transparent, so they can delivery sustainable development and achieve rights for all. This is achieved by promoting accountable systems, fighting corruption and supporting inclusive participation in decision making processes to ensure governments can manage resources effectively, respond to citizen's needs and uphold the rule of law (UNDP, 2021).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Structural Functionalism Theory

Structural functionalism originating from the works of Herbert Spencer, Emile Durkheim, and latter developed by Talcott Parsons, provides a valuable theoretical lens for analyzing political institutions and their functions within a social system (Barnard, 2000). It views society as a system composed of interdependent structures performing necessary functions for systemic stability (Parsons, 1951). Each component of the system serves specific functions that contribute to the overall operation and survival of the system. When applied to political analysis, structural functionalism examines how political institutions function to maintain social order, adapt to changing environments and achieve collective goods..

The core assumptions of structural functionalism are:

- i. **Functional differentiation:** Institutions perform distinct and unique functions
- ii. **Interdependence:** Dysfunction in one structure (institution) affects the entire system
- iii. **System equilibrium:** Stability of the system depends on the effectiveness of institutional roles
- iv. **Adaptation:** Institutions must adjust to environmental demands to remain functional.

The fundamental premise of structural functionalism is that social structures exist to fulfill necessary functions for societal maintenance in the political realm, the legislature, executive and judiciary are like the organs in the human body that functions collectively for the maintains of the system.

Legislatures function not only as lawmaking bodies but also as institutions that express and reinforce societal values through deliberative processes and representative functions.

In political analysis, structural functionalism examines how political structures function to maintain system equilibrium. Political institutions are analyzed in terms of their manifest functions and latent functions. For this study, structural functionalism offers a framework for analyzing how state legislatures contribute to political system maintenance through their core functions:

- i. **Goal Attainment:** Legislatures set collective goals through legislation and policy formulation
- ii. **Adaptation:** They facilitate resource acquisition and allocation through budgetary approval and oversight
- iii. **Integration:** They maintain social solidarity by representing diverse interests and resolving conflicts through democratic processes.
- iv. **Latency:** They preserve and transmit political culture through civic education and legitimization of governance process (McMahon, 2024).

When legislatures cannot perform these functions effectively due to autonomy constraints, systemic dysfunctions emerge; manifesting as governance deficits, political instability and public discontent. Structural functionalism helps diagnose these institutional challenges and recommends functional alternatives for system maintenance. For developing democracies like Nigeria, where institutional strengthening is crucial for democratic consolidation, structural functionalism provides a useful framework for analyzing how political institutions function or malfunction within the broader political system.

This study applies structural functionalism specifically to analyze the relationship between legislative autonomy and governance outcomes in Nigerian States, examining how autonomy constraints hamper functional performance and consequently undermine good governance.

STRUCTURAL FUNCTIONALISM AND LEGISLATIVE FUNCTIONS IN A DEMOCRACY

Within a democratic system, legislatures perform indispensable functions that contribute to system maintenance and equilibrium. Through the structural functionalist lens, these functions can be categorized according to Parson's AGIL (*Adaptation, Goal Attainment, Integration & Latency*) model, revealing how legislatures enable the political system to adapt, achieve goals, maintain integration and preserve cultural patterns. When legislative autonomy is constrained, as in almost all the states in Nigeria, these essential functions are compromised, leading to systemic dysfunctions that manifests as governance deficits.

The legislature play multilateral role in any political system. These includes manifest functions like lawmaking, representation and oversight, and latent functions such as political socialization, elite recruitment and status conferral on government actions. Though some of these functions are clearly stated in the constitution, their effective performance requires substantial autonomy of the legislature, specially financial independence from the executive arm of government.

When legislatures cannot perform their basic functions due to autonomy constraints systemic dysfunctions emerge. Merton (1965) defined dysfunctions as those consequences that lessen the adaptation or adjustment of the system (Lumen, 2022). In Nigerian states, the dysfunction of legislatures are seen in the following forms:

- i. Inadequate oversight of executive implementation of laws and budgets
- ii. Limited representation of constituents interests in policy formulation
- iii. Weak accountability mechanisms for checking the excesses of the executive
- iv. Ineffective conflict resolution through democratic processes.

These dysfunctions create a democratic deficit that undermines public confidence in democratic institutions. As observed by Olaogun, Iwuoha, Umoren, Idoko & Chiazor (2025) "the legislative organ is incapacitated from carrying out effective oversight for good governance because of inadequate autonomy, the executive usurpation of legislative powers by involving in oversight function, the problem of good fatherism and corrupt tendencies of most members of the legislative houses". This is in tandem with structural functionalist analysis which would characterize those constraints as structural imperfections that inhibit functional performance.

The financial dependence of state legislatures on the executive arm of government represents another critical dysfunction point. Without control over their own budgets, legislatures lack the operational independence to effectively check executive power. This creates an imbalance in the separation of powers that structural functionalism would identify as a systemic imperfection requiring structural adjustment for system maintenance. In all, structural functionalism explains why legislative autonomy is essential for maintaining systemic equilibrium and good governance.

LEGISLATIVE AUTONOMY IN NIGERIA STATES: CURRENT REALITIES

The autonomy of state legislatures in Nigeria is circumscribed by constitutional, financial and political constraints that substantially limit their functional capacity. A better comprehension of these constraints is essential for diagnosing the governance challenges in Nigeria states and formulating appropriate interventions. These constraints include:

- i. **Financial Dependence:** State legislature budgets are controlled by state governors who can limit or withhold funding, thereby compromising legislative independence. Legislatures rely on executives for monthly releases and this undermines objectivity in budget oversight.
- ii. **Weak Oversight Performance:** Studies show that most state legislature avoid probing executives even amid clear financial irregularities (Olaleye, 2019).
- iii. **Executive Dominance:** The overwhelming influence of state governors over legislative processes, often through party mechanisms, reduces state houses of assembly to rubber – stamp institutions. Ojo (2018) observed that governors manipulate legislative leadership through financial incentives, impeachment threats and political patronage.
- iv. **Limited Capacity and Resources:** The absence of research units, technical staff and digital infrastructure hinders legislative effectiveness. Legislative performance is hampered when administrative resources are inadequate.
- v. **Corruption:** Misuse of oversight powers for personal gain, and corruption allegations have eroded public trust and compromised the legislatures effectiveness (Ayodele & Akanmu, 2024).
- vi. **Party Politics and Loyalty:** Strong party loyalty and partisan interests often override the public good in legislative decision – making. The dominance of the ruling party can stifle opposition voices and independent legislative initiative, (Ukachukwu & Vande, 2025).
- vii. **High Turnover of Legislators:** High legislative turnover severely constraints legislative autonomy by eroding institutional memory, weakening oversight, disrupting policy continuity and strategic planning, and increasing dependence on the executive (Ibrahim & Abraham, 2025).

LEGISLATIVE AUTONOMY AND GOOD GOVERNANCE

Good governance, characterized by accountability, transparency, responsiveness, and equitable resources allocation, depends significantly on effective legislative performance. Through the structural functionalist lens, legislatures contribute to good governance by performing system – maintenance functions that promote adaptation, goal attainment, integration and latency. When legislative autonomy is constrained, these functions are hampered, leading to poor governance outcomes. The nexus between legislative autonomy and good governance are well illustrated below:

- i. **Fiscal Governance and Public Accountability:** The oversight function of legislatures is crucial for ensuring fiscal discipline and public accountability. Effective legislative oversight minimizes “waste in governance, corruption and absolutism in the exercise of powers” (Olaogun, Iwuoha, Umoren, Idoko & Chiazor, 2025). A functionally autonomous legislature can hold the executive accountable. Structural functionalism posits that accountability is a core system function, and its absence leads to systemic decay. Legislatures enhance transparency by demanding full disclosure of government activities.

When legislatures lack autonomy, their ability to scrutinize executive actions is substantially compromised, resulting to inadequate budget oversight, weak anti – corruption mechanisms and limited public accountability.

The relationship between legislative autonomy and fiscal governance is evident in the management of local government allocations in the states prior to the 11th July, 2024. Supreme Court's pronouncement on local government autonomy (Unwana, 2025). This shows how constrained autonomy of the state legislatures produces negative outcomes that affect citizens wellbeing at the local government level (Asiegbu, 2025).

- ii. **Service Delivery and Development Outcomes:** Legislatures contribute to development outcomes by ensuring that public policies address constituent needs and resources are efficiently allocated. Through their representative function, legislatures channel grassroots demands into policy processes, promoting responsiveness in service delivery. Legislatures shape development policies and respond to citizens needs. Without autonomy development outcomes suffer, as poor policy formulation, inequitable resource allocation and limited service delivery will become the order of the day. The impact of constrained legislative autonomy on service delivery is evident in the declining public trust in governmental institutions. This trust deficit reflects the functional deficiencies in governance institutions that structural functionalism would attribute to structural imperfections inhibiting optimal performance.
- iii. **Political Stability and Democratic Consolidation:** From a structural functionalist perspective, legislatures contribute to political stability by providing institutionalized channels for conflict resolution and interest aggregation. The integrative function of legislatures helps maintain social solidarity by ensuring diverse interests are represented in policy processes. When legislatures perform this function effectively, they enhance regime legitimacy and political stability.

However, when legislatures lack autonomy, these stabilizing functions suffer. Again, a study found out that effective legislative oversight contributes to “the stabilization of politics, reduction of corruption and increasing the quality of democracy” (Olaogwu, Iwoha, Umoren, Idoko & Chiazor; 2025). Conversely, when legislatures cannot perform their oversight functions due to lack of autonomy, the resulting accountability deficits can fuel public discontent and political instability.

LEGISLATIVE AUTONOMY IN NIGERIA: STRUCTURAL CHALLENGES AND CONSEQUENCES

Despite constitutional provisions establishing states Houses of Assembly as independent branches of government at the state levels, several structural and systemic challenges limit their autonomy and functional effectiveness. These challenges have resulted to undesired outcomes affecting good governance at the states and country at large.

CHALLENGES:

i. Political Culture

The political culture does not value and encourage legislative autonomy, thereby creating behavioural norms that undermine institutional autonomy. This culture can be seen in the following instances:

- **Public expectations:** Citizens often look to the state governors rather than the Houses of Assembly for development initiatives, reinforcing executive dominance.
- **Political socialization:** Legislators themselves may internalize subordinate roles, limiting their assertiveness in checking executive power. Both at the national and state levels, the legislators see the President or Governors as the leader and so often depends on them for direction.
- **Party politics:** Strong party structure and discipline pressure legislators to conform to executive preferences rather than exercising independent judgement. In practice, particularly in ruling parties, the party structure is given to the President or Governor. In that capacity, he exercises undue influence over the nomination of party candidates for legislative seats. Ultimately, legislators has to be loyal to secure re – election.

These cultural factors create a path dependency that sustain executive dominance despite formal constitution provisions for separation of powers.

ii. **Institutional Capacity:** State legislatures in Nigeria lack the institutional capacity to carry out their duties effectively even when formal autonomy exists. They lack the technical expertise and necessary administrative systems for effective legislative operations. Also, insufficient funding for legislative activities including constituency outreach and oversight activities hampers functional performance.

iii. **Constitutional Issues:** Constitutional provisions concerning financial independence of state legislatures remain less explicit than those for the National Assembly, creating implementation challenges. Besides the process for constitutional amendment creates significant hurdles for autonomy reforms, requiring approval by two – thirds of state legislatures, many of which may be reluctant to challenge the executive dominance that benefits them and their political patrons.

CONSEQUENCES

A lack of legislative autonomy severely damages structural integrity in the state, undermining the separation of powers and concentrating control within the executive arm. This leads to decreased government accountability, ineffective oversight and a decline in democratic governance (Asimiyu, 2021).

- i. **Systemic Imbalance:** Structural functionalism posits that dysfunction in a single organ affects the entire governance organism. Limited autonomy leads to executive over centralization. In a presidential system like ours, the executive branch's interference with legislative functions has led to a concentration of power with the executive. Today, we see a trend of governors acting with little or no restraint from the houses of assembly.
- ii. **Governance Failure:** Governance failures are seen in form of corruption, weak institutions and poor service delivery. When the executive controls the legislature's finances or influence its members, the system becomes vulnerable to corruption. The absence of checks and effective oversight by the legislature leads to poor project execution and provision of basic services to the people. The situation has a direct effect on the local government system too, as state governments often mismanage or divert funds meant for local councils leading to a lack of basic services and grassroots development.
- iii. **Decline in Public Trust:** When legislative bodies fail to perform their duties and are seen as subservient to the executive, public confidence in democratic institution wanes. Citizens perceive legislatures as extensions of the executive, reducing participation (Olawoyin, 2025).

- iv. **Erosion of Democratic Governance:** In systems lacking autonomy, the subversion of democratic processes, particularly at the local government level is inevitable. This was the reason the use of caretaker committees in running the local governments thrived. Conflicts over control may emerge between the legislature and the executive and this can slow the pace of governance, create hostility and lead to political instability (Momodu & Matudi, 2013). A weak legislature cannot enforce the rule of law against the executive. This fosters a culture of impunity among the political class (Alabi, 2011).

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The constitutional provisions which provide for financial autonomy for the States Houses of Assembly, including direct disbursement of funds from the federation account should be enforced.
- ii. The powers of oversight should be constitutionally and legally strengthened to enhance legislative oversight authority, including subpoena powers and independent audit capabilities.
- iii. The Supreme Court ruling on local government autonomy should be fully implemented beyond having elected local government councils. This would create a more balanced multilevel governance system that reduces excessive concentration of power at state level.
- iv. Regular training and technical assistance programmes should be given to them and their staff to enhance their legislative capacities and effectiveness. Modernization of legislative processes with modern information and communication technologies (ICT) is vital.
- v. The Nigerian state should usher in political reforms that will enhance electoral integrity, promote citizen participation in electoral processes and civil society engagement. Civic education campaigns should be carried out to create an informed citizenry that can demand for legislative accountability.

CONCLUSION

Legislative autonomy is essential for democratic governance, particularly in Nigeria states, where executive dominance is persistent. Structural functionalism demonstrates that state legislatures perform indispensable systemic functions; constraining these functions compromises governance quality. Enhancing legislative autonomy is therefore critical for accountability, transparency, rule of law and service delivery.

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